

Digital Transformation of the System of Higher, Secondary Special Education in Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

The article substantiates the role of the digital transformation of higher education in Uzbekistan in the era of the fourth industrial revolution. There was proven the need to develop the strategy of the university education digital transformation, as well as the formation of new information and communication competencies. According to the authors, the strategy of digital transformation of the university education system has to include the modernization of corporate IT architecture management, which should be implemented as a cloud-based platform. The authors analysed the main possible directions of the educational services transformation and the accompanying business processes. The integration of the educational content management modules of different Uzbekistan university education should become the basis for creating a global cloud-based platform for higher education.

Keywords: information technologies; cloud computing; digital transformation; secondary education; corporate architecture; digital economy; innovative development.

Problem statement. The future of every university education will depend on the availability of resources necessary for the digitalization of the educational environment and the creation of high-quality educational content. At the same time, experts emphasize that there is a danger of an inert attitude towards digitalization in the face of growing demand for education services in developing countries, including Uzbekistan. Over the past several years, digital transformation has become one of the main trends, both in industry and in the public sector of many countries. Digital transformation determines the transition to a massive use of digital technologies in the variety of sectors of the economy and society, which improve or replace traditional products and services digital transformation offers enormous potential for innovation at a rate of several trillion dollars and applies to many industries (e.g., logistics, healthcare, automotive industry) and social trends (e.g., science, government, etc.). The digital transformation of society not only significantly alters

industrial and economic structures, but also introduces new essences in civil, business, state and interstate turnover.

Research by the International Data Corporation shows that by 2025 the total amount of digital data in the world will be 175 zettabytes against 40 zettabytes in 2020 [5]

The result will be an increase in the amount of knowledge available to mankind by 19 times by 2060, that is, today we have 5% of the knowledge that will be created and available to us in 40 years. By 2030, the global economy will attract \$13 trillion only through the development of artificial intelligence, the use of which will provide 14% of global GDP growth (\$15.7 trillion). Today, the global average is 99 robots per 10,000 workers. Over the next 10 years, 60% of all professions will be automated, from 20 million to 50 million jobs will appear in the field of information technology [4].

These forecasts and trends form a high demand for digital and educational services, the relevance of mutual integration of which is today more than ever high, since both areas and their interaction belong to the rank of strategic directions for the development of any growing economy, including Uzbekistan.

The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, critically assessing the state of the potential of the digital economy and the education system in the country, stressed the urgent need for a systematic approach to digitalization at all levels of education in conjunction with priority sectors of the economy - construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, healthcare, as well as in such areas of activity as the cadastre and archives. The President noted the importance of developing the infrastructure of the digital economy, primarily e-government and the system for providing public services online, creating IT parks and training future specialists in the field of the digital economy.

The head of our state noted: "Our top priority should be to create broad opportunities for young people to set ambitious goals and achieve them. Only then will our children become a real force that can fulfill the age-old dreams of our people" [5].

One of the areas that have enormous potential for digital transformation is the university education system, especially the system of higher education. Higher education requires the development of a strategy for digital transformation, and the formation of new information and communication competencies. However, the use of digital technologies in the Uzbekistan higher education is often limited to the creation of multimedia content for lectures and the opening of the access to distance education platforms deployed on the Internet. We believe that the strategy of digital transformation of the higher education system should have a broader focus and has to include the modernization of corporate IT architecture management, which could provide an important contribution to structuring the efforts of innovation in education. Cloud-based platforms of higher education can play an important role in the implementation of the Uzbek education digital transformation and the modernization of traditional educational services. Everything mentioned above indicates the relevance of the chosen topic and outlines the range of issues that require a thorough scientific research.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The theoretical and practical aspects of the digital transformation of society in particular, are covered in the works of such authors as M. WiBotzki, K. Sandkuhl, David Eaves, Valeriy Chumakov, S. Berman, R. Bell, A. Kuntzman, N. Rozanova, A. Yushyn, G. Karcheva, S. Veretiuk etc.

The main directions of the influence of digital transformation on the evolution of social and economic systems are:

- increasing mobility in satisfying the needs of consumers, allowing to overcome the territorial restrictions and dependence on the location of service providers [5];

- obtaining the possibility of collecting, storing and processing large volumes of information, which leads to a reduction of transaction costs in decision-making and concluding transactions;
- proliferation of network effects, that change the chains of generating profits and underlie new business models;
- changing the system of relations between consumers and service providers towards the involvement of consumers in the process of creating a new consumer value, for example, under the concept of "open innovation".

However, existing studies do not fully take into account the peculiarities of the creation and modernization of corporate IT architecture of higher education, as well as the emergence and development of cloud-based higher schools platforms that can play an important role in the process of digital transformation Uzbekistan education The purpose of the article is to study the features and define the main criteria for the higher education system digital transformation in the context of transition of the domestic socio-economic system to the innovative nature of development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on the use of general scientific and theoretical methods: analysis and synthesis of scientific, technical and pedagogical literature concerning the digital transformation of society and its impact on the system of higher or secondary special education; the combination of theories and conclusions from various fields of research. The paper uses argumentative- deductive, inductive and systematic approaches.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Human capital is the most valuable resource of modern society. More than 35 million people live in the republic, of which 18 million (more than 60%) are young people under the age of 30. According to preliminary forecasts, by 2030 the population of Uzbekistan will increase to 40 million people, of which, if the trend continues, 24 million will be young people. In addition, the President set the task of turning Uzbekistan into a regional IT center. In this regard, great attention is paid to attracting young people to the field of IT education.

According to the World Bank, the digital economy is a system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital information and communication technologies. The widespread proliferation of digital technologies, their penetration into basically all spheres of human life and society is reflected in the concept of digital transformation. In the era of the fourth industrial revolution, the most important factor - the factor of access to advanced technologies - was added to traditional advantages in the form of inclusive institutions and strong leaders. The technological explosion leads to qualitative changes in business and management[6]

In many industries, products and services are traditionally supplied on the basis of physical infrastructure (for example, shops, banking offices, service centres, universities) or individuals (for example, dealers, brokers, academics, lecturers). Often, products or services are also physically displayed, and operational processes use physical support. In this context, digital transformation determines the transition from traditional creation and sales of services to clients, including related operational procedures, to the use of digital technologies to enhance or replace traditional services with digital ones.

The basis of modern digital enterprises will be the technology of the so-called third platform: cloud computing, mobile services, "brainfacturing", i.e., intellectual production, big data, the concept of IoT (Internet of Things) and social networks.

For the further analysis of the directions of digital transformation. This approach addresses two aspects of digital transformation: the transformation of products and services offered by organizations and the transformation of business processes for the provision of these products, in

both aspects, they are distinguished by three stages. In the aspect of transformation of products and services, the following stages are distinguished: improvement (adding additional services), expansion (adding new features of existing products or services through digital components), and redefining (creating new products or services that replace the previous ones). In the aspect of business processes, the stages are as follows: creation (the emergence of new business processes on the basis of IT), leverage (the emergence of new opportunities to achieve greater efficiency of business processes) and integration (the combination of new and traditional business processes into a single infrastructure).

Over the past five years, the number of universities has reached 160 and, according to the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, this number will increase to 200. A unified integrated electronic system (HEMIS), which was created within the framework of a World Bank project, has also been created. It includes a database of all students in the republic (including private and international universities), their attendance and performance, as well as the country's teachers, electronic resources, academic programs, educational content and more.

Digital education at Inha University in Tashkent (IUT), established in 2014 as the first educational institution of the Republic of Korea abroad, involves the introduction of digital technologies into the continuous process of training international IT specialists. This innovative choice of training involves not only the use of modern technical equipment or software, but also a fundamental change in existing electronic platforms using AI and with the aim of making training programs more flexible and in demand for employers.

Assuming that the overall goal of digital transformations in the system of higher education is the transformation of educational services and the accompanying business processes, there are three different possible directions that need to be analysed:

- transformation and redefinition of educational services to match the changes in the system of business processes of the higher schools;
- transformation of business processes aimed at creating new and improving the existing IT-based business processes as the basis for further analysis and transformation of eduk services;
- combining the first and second directions in order to integrate the simultaneous transformation in both directions.

The first direction mainly requires digitization of all major and most of the auxiliary educational services. Creating profits in higher institutions is primarily related to the educational process and students (i.e. higher schools admission, the choice of curricula and courses, the results of examinations, etc.), as well as the development of curricula and programs and ensuring their quality. Supporting educational services include: financial management, training planning, academic training scheduling and many other functions. In general, this normally requires creation or implementation of an integrated management system for higher education, including support for mobile workers and asset management of the higher reating new services and converting existing services into digital ones. An integral part of this process is the opening of implemented curricula for access outside the higher education institution at the national and international levels. Usually, this involves the creation of digital educational content and the provision of digital interaction and collaboration between students and faculty as well as students between themselves. Internationalization of services also requires adaptation while using the different languages. In addition, most traditional educational programs should be distributed to lower-level programmes, for example, instead of four-year curricula for shorter individual certification programs, or instead of six ECTS training modules, smaller, but combined modules. Such a division will allow the sale of services to a wider audience and increase their flexibility.

In the case of a combination of two directions, their systematic interconnection is established. For example, it may be the creation of a new group at the for higher choools to conduct research on a grant, in a combination with the digital transformation of business processes related to a new direction or field of research and the financing of its work.

An analysis of the impact of digital transformation on the for higher school's IT architecture makes it possible to draw the following conclusions:

- The for higher schools business process system requires the creation of a directory of administrative services for the training process and internal research, personnel management, infrastructure management and other support services. Also, it is necessary to take into account all stages of the student's life cycle in the system of business processes (from admission to higher schools to graduation).
- The software application architecture requires the creation of an integrated student life cycle management system, the integration of administrative information systems with systems of planning and management of curricula and modules, databases of scientific data and library repositories. The best way to implement such a system is to create a cloud-based platform for the higher schools.
- The data architecture requires the creation of a publicly available data model with the opportunities for exchange between the universities (for example, for managing the student life cycle, for administrative purposes, for content of lectures, etc.). In modern conditions, educational materials are already created in the form of multimedia, digital content, but often are not integrated with administrative data.
- Technology architecture in the context of digital transformation requires the creation of a centralized IT infrastructure of the higher choools established on a cloud-based platform with additional separate platforms for technology parks and research units.

The largest change is needed in the architecture of software applications, which should be implemented as a new cloud-based platform for the delivery of innovative scientific products and educational services. This can be implemented through collaborative cloud- based support in the divided student groups that cannot attend classes in higher schools buildings and are geographically distributed. The digital transformation process will also be affected by the business processes: for example, the formalization of the online exams procedure and the development of modified work processes for issuing the diplomas, certificates, etc. However, most of the traditional higher management functions should remain stable. In the data architecture, one of the important transformations will be the more intensive use of digital content and the integration of different types of data with administrative databases and student registers.

The digital transformation process focuses on the digitization of all revenue-generating processes and supporting business processes that affect the business from the point of view of IT architecture of the p higher schools. For a business process system, the implementation of digital processes and their optimization is just one of the issues that needs to be addressed. Adaptation of the higher schools organizational structure to change in the business processes, creation of new organizational units for online educational programs or conducting the certified courses are equally important, higher education communication competence.

For the combined directions of digital transformation, the alteration of services and business processes is initially performed on the basis of separate units or clearly defined individual institutions. An example is the beginning of a digital transformation of only the Master's training system or the modification of internationally oriented training programmes. There is also the possibility of new training formats, such as short curricula (up to one semester) for mixed target groups, in the form of a combination of traditional study and online learning.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis, we can conclude that the educational content management system can serve as an integration point for the implementation of the digital transformation strategy. New target groups of students and educational services formats require adapted support for learning management systems in comparison with the traditional student groups, since the teaching and tuition concepts and materials will be different from the traditional ones. In our opinion, in order to facilitate this adaptation, the higher schools's educational content management system should be flexibly adapted to the student's individual needs, and integrate existing and future learning process essentials tools that support different phases of learning.

In our opinion, further research should include a step-by-step analysis of transformational measures and analysis of all layers of IT architecture of higher education institutions, including the calculation of the economic effect of digital transformation at all its levels. It is also necessary to investigate the digital transformation of other organizations of secondary and vocational education in higher schools platform of Uzbekistan. Over the next two decades, new technologies and digitalisation processes will generally change the approach to education, and we need to take measures today to prepare for these changes

Further digital transformation of the university, meeting the requirements of the future, must be competitive, competing for the attention of new consumers of IT personnel in the labor market. Such a concept of digital transformation of the university MUST be reflected in the new strategy.

Let us note several of the most important tasks of the State University of Economics regarding digitalization of education

- Creation of new popular training courses and international programs. Opening an IT school at the university, as well as e-sports laboratories for students and students of specialized schools.
- Improving cooperation with BPO companies, as well as arranging co-working and coloring areas in open space style for students.
- Stimulating gifted students using the opportunities of start-up projects and venture financing implemented at the University Incubation Center with the involvement of sponsors, as well as the creation of venture funds.
- Introduction of courses from Coursera, Udemy, SAP, Oracle, Cisco, IBM academies into the educational process.

References:

1. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан № ПП-5157 от 22 июня 2021 года «О параметрах заказа по приему в высшие учебные образовательные учреждения Республики Узбекистан в 2021–2022 учебном году». [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/5472308> (дата обращения:01.08.2021).
2. Shadibekova, D. (2019). Foreign investments and innovative development - is the most important factor in expanding uzbekistan's production capacities. *Архив научных исследований*, 1(1). извлечено от <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/479>
3. Ержанбек А., Ташкын Е., Бердыгулова А. Д., Елеусизова Г. С. Эволюция инновационного развития и глобальное будущее образования в эпоху цифровизации // *Wschodnioeuropejskie czasopismo naukowe*. – 2020. – № 5-3 (57).
4. Нуритдинова В.Ш. Цифровая экономика и ее роль в системе образования // *Экономика и бизнес: теория и практика*. – 2021. – № 1-2. – с. 18-15.

5. Индустрия 4.0 в 40 цифрах. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/trends/industry/5daef6429a7947c1bfe43006> (дата обращения: 01.08.2021).
6. D.Shadibekova Challenges on digital economy in sample of various income economies as an development instrument in Uzbekistan June 2019 ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 09 (65): 388-393.DOI 10.31150/ajebm.Vol2.Iss2.66
7. The Digitization of the World – From Edge to Core. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.seagate.com/gb/en/our-story/data-age-2025/> (дата обращения: 01.08.2021).
8. <https://www.worldbank.org>